

iJEResearch

International Journal of Education and Research

Vol. 1, Number 3, December - 2025 | Peer-Reviewed Journal

ISSN 2764-9733 | ijerresearch.org

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18095171

THE USE OF PUPPETS AS A STORYTELLING TOOL IN ART CLASSES FOR CREATIVE DEVELOPMENT, FOR 3RD GRADE ELEMENTARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

AUTHORS

Ednaldo Carmo dos Santos: Master in Performing Arts from the Célia Helena Higher School of Arts-BR; Master's student in Education Sciences at UNIDA University -PY; Psychopedagogue; Art Therapist; Head of the Cultural Mediation sector of the Franco da Rocha City Hall -SP ; Professor of the subject "Methodology of Arts Teaching" at the Conchas Faculty-BR; Researcher in Animated Forms Theatre.

Contact: ed.carmo@hotmail.com | +55(11)99770-5336

Irineia Monteiro da Silva: PhD candidate in Educational Sciences at UNIDA University -PY; Master's degree in Educational Sciences from Columbia University – PY; Basic Education Teacher, responsible for the Special Education Program at EMEB José Augusto Moreira in the municipality of Franco da Rocha-SP ; Specialist in Special Education.

Contact: neia2007monteiro@gmail.com | +55(11)96983-6348

ABSTRACT

This article investigates the use of puppets as a pedagogical tool in art classes for the creative development of 3rd-grade elementary school students. Based on the premise that storytelling and play are fundamental to the learning process, the study analyzes how the making and manipulation of puppets influence student engagement, artistic expression, and social interaction. The qualitative research was conducted through participant observation and semi-structured interviews with 32 students from a municipal public school. The results indicate that the use of puppets significantly increased interest in classes, stimulated creativity in narrative creation, strengthened peer cooperation, and facilitated the expression of emotions and ideas. It concludes that the inclusion of this tool in art lesson planning constitutes an effective strategy for creating a dynamic, interactive learning environment conducive to the holistic development of students.

Keywords: Art Education. Puppets. Storytelling. Creativity. Elementary Education.